
JRP16-ET2.2-TELEVIR

Work package 4

Responsible Partners: SSI

Contributing partners: All partners

GENERAL INFORMATION

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Leader	Morten Rasmussen and Katja Spiess (SSI)
Other contributors	All partners
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The POI protocol developed in the Televir project includes virus inactivation, nucleic acid extraction, DNase pretreatment, random amplification, library preparation, and a sequencing protocol for metagenomic detection of RNA/DNA viruses. The steps of the POI protocol are described in a Standard Operating Protocol (SOP) that is available on Zenodo (DOI number). For the proof of concept studies, the Rapid Sequencing Kit was used for RNA/DNA virus detection, as it is field employable. In the event of a potential outbreak, the POI toolbox can be used to rapidly detect viruses in individual or pooled samples.

In WP4 nine TELEVIR partners collected samples and performed proof of concept/field studies to test the POI toolbox. The studies were conducted on a total of 146 samples from more than 25 species detecting both RNA and DNA viruses. A short overview of the sample collection and proof of concept/field studies are listed below:

Some of the TELEVIR partners applied further changes to the POI protocol for example based on their existing laboratory structure. To be able to compare the results we categorized them in the table below:

Table 1 Classification of changes applied to the POI protocol

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minor	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• filter pore size changed• frozen sample material• Rapid Barcoding kit• use of a non-field-employable RNA/DNA quantification device (e.g. spectrometer)• no or additional filtration steps
major	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• no pretreatment with DNase• extraction-, random amplification or- sequencing method changed• additional purification steps after the random amplification step

Sample collection and proof of concept studies/field studies (WP4)

ANSES collected swabs and tissue material from fish and conducted two studies. In the first study, the

POI protocol with major modifications detected a DNA virus in swabs from gills of infected carp. In the second study, the POI protocol with major modifications detected a DNA virus in tissues from infected sturgeon. One issue encountered was the low ratio of target/other DNA, which made it difficult to detect DNA viruses in fish, but could be based on the changes applied to the POI protocol.

PIWET collected swabs from mink and liver (both were frozen). They conducted two studies on viruses in mink and wild boar. In the first study, the POI protocol without modifications successfully detected a DNA virus in mink samples collected from farm environments. In the second study, the POI protocol without modifications confirmed the presence of a virus in an archive sample of wild boar organ homogenate (2/3 samples), as well as non expected viruses were detected. Failures in virus detection (1 sample) during sequencing may have been due to degradation (working with frozen sample material) or inefficient amplification of viral DNA/RNA.

INIA collected as proof of concept feathers and oral swabs from birds during an *in vivo* study. Moreover, they included a human blood plasma sample from a diseased patient. In the first study, the POI protocol with minor modifications successfully detected a RNA virus in feathers and oral swabs from infected partridges. In the second study, the POI protocol with minor and major modifications did not detect a virus in a human sample with an unknown infection. One issue is the low ratio *target/other* DNA (host, bacteria, phages, etc.). Quantification is an essential step, especially by following the Nanopore Rapid Barcoding kit in order to load the same amount of DNA/cDNA of the samples.

IZLER collected samples from turkey, mallard and cattle (tracheal and nasal swabs) and a tissue sample from a pig. They led 5 different studies on viruses in wildlife and domestic animals. The POI protocol without modifications successfully detected viruses in the collected samples.

IZSAM collected samples from cattle and deer and led two field studies using the POI protocol with minor modifications. In the first study, the protocol was applied to samples from cattle and deer with clinical signs of infection and successfully identified the viral species involved in the infection. In the second study, the protocol was applied to a tissue sample from a pig with skin lesions and also here identified virus associate with the infection.

UoS applied the POI protocol with minor modifications to samples from previously frozen animal carcasses from a zoological collection and but failed to detect any viruses. The high level of chemical carryover in the samples may have affected the results.

SSI collected samples from animals of a zoo and tested the POI protocol with minor modifications. They detected successfully viruses in 18 samples from 10 animal species. Freshness of the sample material seemed to be crucial for viral detection success.

SVA collected samples from poultry and wild boar and applied the POI protocol with minor modifications. They failed to detect the the expected viruses in the samples.

NVI collected fecal samples from birds and samples from animals with unknown infections to test the

POI toolbox. The samples were collected opportunistically from the environment, from dead birds as part of routine diagnostics, and from live animals in animal facilities. The POI protocol was modified with the addition of larger filter pores and the use of the Nanopore Rapid Barcoding kit for a portion of the study, and with the omission of the initial DNase treatment for another portion of the study. The results from these studies are to be evaluated.

Conclusion

In WP4 all TELEVIR partners collected a variety of samples and performed the proof of concept/field studies using the POI toolbox developed in WP2 and WP3. Overall, the results of the proof of concept studies demonstrate the effectiveness of the POI toolbox and the different library preparation and Oxford-Nanopore protocols in detecting various viruses in a variety of samples. TELEVIR partners that did not succeed of applying the POI toolbox will be guided by TELEVIR partners that had already experience in metagenomic sequencing and samples will be tested in parallel by different TELEVIR partners. The INSaFLU-TELEVIR platform developed in WP2 is publically available. This platform has been successfully used in the proof of concept/field studies to evaluate the sequencing data.